

Vulnerability to Climate Shocks and Its Determinants: Insights from Farming Households in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines the vulnerability of farming households in Nigeria to climate shocks, a critical challenge affecting agricultural productivity and food security in developing regions. Using data from the Nigeria General Household Survey (GHS-Panel) across waves 2-4, the study profiles households based on socio-economic characteristics and evaluates the determinants of vulnerability through a Three-Stage Feasible Generalized Least Squares (3-SFGLS) model. The results reveal that over 61% of farming households are vulnerable to climate shocks, with significant contributing factors including poor rainfall, flooding, farmer-herder conflicts, limited access to credit, and low levels of education. Vulnerable households often exhibit smaller farm sizes, reliance on informal credit, and limited adaptive capacity, highlighting the critical role of socio-economic and institutional barriers. The study underscores the importance of targeted interventions, such as improving access to climate-resilient farming practices, expanding formal credit access, enhancing education, and strengthening community-based adaptation mechanisms. These findings provide actionable insights for policymakers and stakeholders seeking to enhance household resilience and ensure sustainable agricultural development amidst increasing climate variability.

Keywords: *Climate Shocks, Food Security, Vulnerability, Socioeconomic Factors, Three-Stage Feasible Generalized Least Squares.*

1. Introduction

The vulnerability to climate shocks is closely linked to the high reliance on agricultural livelihoods and widespread poverty in many regions (Wossen *et al.*, 2018). Climate shocks have emerged as a significant global challenge, with disasters occurring more frequently in high-income countries but having more severe impacts on low-income nations (Ogbonna *et al.*, 2017; Thomas and López, 2015). Climate change refers to long-term alterations in the earth's climate, including shifts in temperature, precipitation patterns, sea levels, and atmospheric conditions. These changes are typically observed over decades to centuries. Climate change and associated shocks are increasingly recognized as drivers of food insecurity (Brown *et al.*, 2015).

Extreme climate events become more frequent and widespread. It is an unusual and severe weather or climate events that occur at the upper or lower ends of the range of observed climate parameters (Robinson and Historic, 2013; Coumou and Rahmstorf, 2012). The impacts of climate change and extreme events on agriculture are multifaceted and occur at various scales (Brown *et al.*, 2015). While long-term warming trends are projected to significantly affect crop yields, especially in tropical regions, over multiple decades (Challinor *et al.*, 2014), climate "shocks" pose more immediate and severe threats to household food security. These shocks, defined as events that overwhelm a society's coping capacity, include droughts, floods, and heat waves (Mehtar *et al.*, 2016).

Climate variability refers to the natural fluctuations in climate parameters (like temperature, rainfall, and wind) over shorter periods. These fluctuations occur around the long-term climate average. It manifests in higher temperatures, altered precipitation patterns, and more frequent, prolonged, and intense extreme weather events like floods, droughts, and heat waves (Stocker *et al.*, 2013). These changes pose substantial threats to global food security in both rural and urban areas by affecting agricultural production, food prices, and food system infrastructure (Hertel *et al.*, 2010; Lesk *et al.*, 2016; Porter *et al.*, 2014; Wheeler and Von Braun, 2013). Droughts are particularly detrimental to food production, accounting for over 80% of natural hazard-induced crop and livestock losses (FAO *et al.*, 2018).

The IPCC (2014) notes that vulnerability to climate shocks is amplified by factors such as poverty, inequitable resource access, food insecurity, conflict, and the prevalence of diseases like malaria and Ebola. This vulnerability is intrinsically tied to the widespread dependence on

agricultural livelihoods and pervasive poverty in many regions (Wossen *et al.*, 2018). Climate shocks have become a significant global issue, with a paradoxical pattern: disasters occur more frequently in high-income countries but inflict more severe damage in low-income nations (Ogbonna *et al.*, 2017; Thomas and López, 2015).

The specific objectives of this study are to:

- Profile the socio-economics characteristics based on vulnerability to climate shocks in Nigeria.
- Profile the level of households based on vulnerability status to climate shocks in Nigeria.
- Examine the determinant of vulnerability to climate shocks in Nigeria.

2. Insights from the Empirical Literature

Vishnu *et al.*, (2019) studied climate shocks in Western Nepal using household data and climatological analysis. Household data provided a rich understanding of the currently perceived climatic shocks and related events. The analysis of climatology was carried out through nine indices of precipitation and temperature that were found to be relevant to the discussed climate shocks using Sen's slope and Mann-kendle test. Results show that 79% of households reported experiencing at least one type of climate shock in the five-year period and the most common occurrence was droughts, which is also supported by the climate data. Disaggregated results show that perception varies with the region and among the basins. Analysis of climatic trends further show that irregular weather is most common in the hill region, although average reported frequency of irregular weather is higher in the mountain. Majority of respondents lack proper access to knowledge and that successful adaptation strategies must be adapted to specific regions to meet communities' local needs.

Niles and Salerno (2018) conducted a cross-country analysis of climate shocks and smallholder food insecurity across 15 countries in Latin America, Africa, and South Asia. A multilevel statistical model was used to estimate factors correlated with food insecurity among households that had experienced a climate shock. Their results showed that households that reported experiencing climate shock were 1.73 times more likely to be food insecure. The results demonstrate the extent of existing climate shocks affecting smallholder farmers and how interventions may potentially support adaptation and reduce food insecurity. Lokonon (2017) examined farmers' vulnerability to climate shocks in the Niger Basin of Benin using an integrated

approach. Integrated approach was used to assess the vulnerability to climate shocks as function of exposure, sensitivity and adaptive capacity, and the indices are used as dependent variable in an Ordinary Least Squares Regression. The findings revealed that 57.43% of the farm households are vulnerable to climate shocks, and highlight that the lowest adaptive capacity does not necessarily coincide with highest exposure and sensitivity to result in the highest vulnerability. The econometric estimations showed that vulnerability levels increase differently with respect to the type of climate shock.

Furthermore, Onyenekwe (2018) investigated the impact of climate shocks, environmental degradation, and resource conflict on food security in Nigeria's Niger Delta region. Employing survey data collected from Rivers and Bayelsa States. He investigated the vulnerability of the farming and fishing households to the triple challenge of climate shock, resource conflict and environmental degradation, and how these challenges undermine food security needs of various occupation groups in the study area. Ratio analysis was used to analyzed the vulnerability levels of the households, ordered logit model was employed to access the effect of vulnerability on the food security status of households and multinomial logit model was used to determine factors affecting the household choice of adaptation strategies. The results show that farming and fishing households have the similar vulnerability score, 0.42 and 0.43 respectively.

Ayinde *et al.*, (2018) investigated maize farmers' vulnerability to climate risk. it specifically determines their knowledge of climate change; examines their vulnerability; identifies the determinants of vulnerability and their management strategies. Descriptive statistics, Likert scale, vulnerability index and stepwise regression were the tools of analysis. Result showed that, majority of the farmers agreed that the climate is changing which is corroborated by the meteorological data analyzed. The vulnerability assessment shows that the farmers are vulnerable. The results also showed that farmers do not have the necessary capacity to mitigate against the effect of climate change. It therefore recommends that adequate climatic information, easy access to drought tolerant maize variety should be prioritize in policy making.

These studies collectively demonstrate the widespread interest in understanding climate shocks' impacts on agriculture and food security, particularly in developing regions. They employ various methodologies, from household surveys to statistical modeling, to assess vulnerability and identify potential adaptation strategies.

3. Research Methodology

The study uses secondary data from the Nigeria General Household Survey panel component (GHS-Panel), waves 2-4. This data was obtained from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). The sample consists of 703 rural household respondents. Respondents were randomly selected from the six geo-political zones in Nigeria. There is a note about wide disparity in sample sizes, attributed to a significant amount of missing data. The study includes various variables, which can be categorized as follows: Socioeconomic factors such as food security status, farming household income, farm size, access to resources, education level, age, gender and household size. Climate and environmental factors includes poor rain patterns, flooding and pest invasion.

The descriptive statistics was used to profile the socio-economic characteristics based on vulnerability to climate shocks, composite score to profile household vulnerability levels to climate shocks, while 3-stage FGLS was adopted to analyzing the determinant of vulnerability to climate shocks in Nigeria. This method is particularly useful when dealing with potential heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation in the data. The combination of these methods allows for a comprehensive analysis, from basic data description to complex statistical modeling, addressing different aspects of the research questions related to climate shocks, vulnerability, and food insecurity in Nigeria.

Vulnerability to climate shocks was calculated using a three-step process following Capaldo *et al.*, (2010). This study adapted the three-step process used by Capaldo *et al.*, (2010). Let C_h indicate climate shock (food stability which represents the food security line) of an individual household, h and X_h be vectors of observable household characteristic such as drought, flooding, heat wave etc. Thus, the individual household’s food stability can be mathematically expressed as follows:

$$C_h = X_h\beta = \beta_1x_{h1} + \dots + \beta_2x_{h2} + \dots + \beta_jx_{hj} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where β is a vector of parameters for the households, and when we consider all households in a single multivariate equation, we get:

$$C = X\beta = \begin{cases} \beta_1x_{11} + \dots + \beta_2x_{12} + \dots + \beta_jx_{1j} \\ \beta_1x_{h1} + \dots + \beta_2x_{h2} + \dots + \beta_jx_{hj} \\ \beta_1x_{H1} + \dots + \beta_2x_{H2} + \dots + \beta_jx_{Hj} \end{cases} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where $C = [c_1 \dots c_h \dots c_H]$ and $X = [X \dots X_h \dots X_H]$

The first step in the three-step generalized least squares (GLS) method is to estimate the multivariate equation and obtain the estimated $\hat{\beta}$ of the parameters that describe climate shock, the residual component was computed from equation below.

$$U = [u_1 \dots u_h \dots u_h] \quad C = [X\hat{\beta} + u] \text{-----} (3)$$

As a second step, their dependence on the same explanatory variables (X_S) through a set of parameters, $\hat{\beta}$ as presented in equation: $u = X\hat{\beta} + \varepsilon$ will be assessed.

Where ε is the residuals of equation, depicting residuals' properties that u does not have. Looking at the deterministic part of the equation $u = X\hat{\beta} + \varepsilon$ after heteroscedasticity has been corrected for, one can derive a consistent estimate of the household variance of food consumption $\hat{\sigma}_u^2$. In the last step, $\hat{\sigma}_u^2$ is used to compute each household's vulnerability to food insecurity.

Assuming that vulnerability distributes normally, each household's probability of food insecurity is given by a determination in equation as:

$$v_h \sim N(E(uh), \hat{\sigma}_u^2) \text{-----} (4)$$

In this context for a given household h , the vulnerability is defined as the probability that each household faces the challenge of falling below the minimum energy requirement in the future.

4 Result and Discussion

Socio-Economic Characteristics of the Respondents

The results showing the distribution of the respondents based on their personal and socio-economics characteristics as well as vulnerability to climate shocks are presented sequentially and discussed in this section.

The results in Table 1 revealed the age distribution among the farming households. The findings showed that in wave 2, 25.09% of the non-vulnerable group and 23.56% of the vulnerable group were above age 60 years, while approximately 24% and 21.6% of both non-vulnerable and vulnerable group respectively, were also within the age range of 41-50 years. The results also indicated that 21.6% of non-vulnerable group and 23.80% of vulnerability group were within age range 31.4 years, while 21.3% of the non-vulnerable group and 20.43% of vulnerability group were also between age range 51-60 years. Then, 8.01% of the non-vulnerable group and approximately 10.6% of the vulnerable group were within age range of less than or equal to 30

years of age. In general, the results indicated that, vulnerable households have a slightly younger age distribution with more individuals in the 31-40 range, while non-vulnerable households have a higher concentration of elderly individuals (above 60).

The findings in wave 3 showed that, 23.60% of the non-vulnerable group and 24.50% of the vulnerable group were above 60 years, while approximately 21.2% and 23.4% of both non-vulnerable and vulnerable group respectively, were also within age range 41-50 years. The results also indicated that 26.00% of the non-vulnerable group and 21.19% of the vulnerable group were within age range 31-40 years, while 22.40% of the non-vulnerable group and 19.87% of the vulnerable group were also between age range of 51-60 years. Then, 6.80% of the non-vulnerable group and approximately 11.00% of the vulnerable group were within age range of less than or equal to 30 years of age. In general, the results indicated that, vulnerable households in wave 3 have a higher concentration of elderly individuals (Above 60), while non-Vulnerable households show a shift towards younger individuals, particularly in the 31-40 age group.

The age distribution of the non-vulnerable and the vulnerable households in wave 4 showed that, 24.06% and 18.76% of both non-vulnerable and vulnerable group respectively, were between age range of 51-60 years, while approximately 22.2% and 23.3% respectively were within age range 31-40 years. The results also revealed that, 22.93% of the non-vulnerable and 24.94% of the vulnerable group were above age 60 years while approximately 21.8% and 23.1% were between age range 41-50 years. Then, 9.02% of the non-vulnerable group and 9.84% of the vulnerable group were within age range of less than or equal to 30 years. This shows that, there is a slight increase in the 51-60 age group, while the above 60 age group remains significant but not the largest in non-vulnerable households.

The mean age of the respondents were 50.4 years. It is believed that younger people commit more energy to production activities, while older farmers are likely to be more experienced. The findings are in line with Atedhor (2015) who in a related study on Agricultural vulnerability to climate change in Sokoto State, Nigeria, also reiterated the predominance of young population groups in the farming workforce in that area.

Table 1: Profiling of age group of the farming household vulnerability (n = 703)

Age group	Wave 2		Wave 3		Wave 4		Pooled	
	Non-vulnerable	Vulnerable	Non-vulnerable	Vulnerable	Non-vulnerable	Vulnerable	Frequency	Percentage
<=30	8.01	10.58	6.80	11.04	9.02	9.84	67	9.53
31-40	21.60	23.80	26.00	21.19	22.18	23.34	161	22.90
41-50	24.04	21.63	21.20	23.40	21.80	23.11	159	22.62
51-60	21.25	20.43	22.40	19.86	24.06	18.76	146	20.77
Above60	25.09	23.56	23.60	24.50	22.93	24.94	179	24.18
Mean							50.4	
Total	287	416	250	453	266	437	703	100.00

Source: Author's Computation 2024

The findings in table 2 showed that 44.95% and of both non-vulnerable and vulnerable group in wave 2 were female, while 55.05% were male. Likewise, in wave 3, 44.40% of the non-vulnerable and 45.25% of the vulnerable group were female while approximately 55.6% of non-vulnerable and 54.8% of the vulnerable group were male. This indicated the predominance of male headed families compared to their female counterparts. For wave 4, 45.86% of non-vulnerable and 44.39% of vulnerable were female while 54.14% and 55.61% respectively were male. This shows that, across all waves, the gender distribution between male and female remains almost identical, with males slightly out numbering females in both vulnerable and non-vulnerable groups.

Table 2: Profiling of gender distribution of the farming household vulnerability (n = 703)

Gender	Wave 2		Wave 3		Wave 4		Pooled	
	Non-vulnerable	Vulnerable	Non-vulnerable	Vulnerable	Non-vulnerable	Vulnerable	Frequency	Percentage
Female	44.95	44.95	44.40	45.25	45.86	44.39	316	44.95
Male	55.05	55.05	55.60	54.75	54.14	55.61	387	55.05
Total	287	416	250	453	266	437	703	100.00

Source: Author's Computation 2024

Table 3 shows the analysis of farming households based on their size in wave 2, wave 3 and wave 4 and divided them into two groups: Non-vulnerable and Vulnerable group. In wave 2, 50.52% of the non-vulnerable and 55.05% were between range of 6-10 members which was the largest category within the wave. Approximately 36.6% of the non-vulnerable and 32.00% of the vulnerable group were in the range of less than or equal to 5 members, while, 12.89% and 12.98% respectively had above 10 members. This revealed that, most vulnerable households fell between the range of 6-10 members, but with a slightly higher percentage compared to the non-vulnerable group. This shows that larger households (6-10 members) were more common among the vulnerable group.

Furthermore, results from wave 3 revealed that, 51.60% of the non-vulnerable group and 54.08% of the vulnerable group were range between 6-10 members, 39.60% of the non-vulnerable group and 30.68% of the vulnerable group had family size of less than or equal to 5 members, while approximately 8.8% of the non-vulnerable group and 15.2% of the vulnerable group were above 10 members. This indicated that, vulnerable households tend to have slightly larger household sizes, with a notable increase in the percentage of households with more than 10 members. In wave 4, 30.83% of the non-vulnerable group and 35.70% of the vulnerable group had household of less than or equal to 5 members, 53.76% and 52.86% of both non-vulnerable and vulnerable respectively had the family size between 6-10 members while 15.41% of non-vulnerable and 11.44% of vulnerable group household size were above 10 members. This shows a slight shift in household size distribution across both groups, with non-vulnerable households showing an increase in larger household sizes and vulnerable households showing a moderate rise in smaller households (≤ 5 members).

The mean household size of the farmers was 6.9 members which implies that there exists approximately 7 members in every farming household in the study area. This agrees with Enete and Okon (2010) who also reported that more than half (60%) of the farmers had household size ranging between 5-8 persons, in a related study conducted in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 3: Profiling the household size of the farming household vulnerability (n = 703)

Household size	Wave 2		Wave 3		Wave 4		Pooled	
	Non-vulnerable	Vulnerable	Non-vulnerable	Vulnerable	Non-vulnerable	Vulnerable	Frequency	Percentage
<=5	36.59	31.97	39.60	30.68	30.83	35.70	238	33.85
6-10	50.52	55.05	51.60	54.08	53.76	52.86	374	53.20
Above 10	12.89	12.98	8.80	15.23	15.41	11.44	91	12.94
Mean								6.9
Total	286	416	250	453	266	437	703	100.00

Source: Author's Computation 2024

The results in table 4 showed that, in wave 2, 44.6% of the non-vulnerable households and 48.32% of the vulnerable group had farmland of less than or equal to 1 hectare, 19.51% of the non-vulnerable group and 12.98% of the vulnerable group had farmland of 1-3 hectares, 20.91% of non-vulnerable group and 19.47% of vulnerable group cultivated farmland of 3-5 hectares, while approximately 15.00% and 19.2% of both non-vulnerable and vulnerable group respectively cultivated farmland of above 5 hectares of land. Furthermore, wave 3 revealed that, 39.20% of the non-vulnerable and 50.99% of the vulnerable group cultivated about 1 hectare, 16.80% and 15.01% of both non-vulnerable and vulnerable group respectively had farmland of between the range of 1-3 hectares, 23.60% of the non-vulnerable group and 18.10% of the vulnerable group cultivated 3-5 hectares of farmlands while approximately, 20.4% of the non-vulnerable group and 15.9% of the vulnerable group cultivated above 5 hectares of farmland.

Wave 4 non-vulnerable and vulnerable group showed that, 47.74% and 46.22% both non-vulnerable and vulnerable respectively cultivated about 1 hectare of farmland, 14.29% of the non-vulnerable group and 16.48% of the vulnerable group cultivated farmland of between range of 1-3 hectares, 22.56% and 18.54% of both non-vulnerable and vulnerable respectively cultivated farmland of between 3-5 hectares, while approximately 15.4% and 18.8% respectively cultivated farmland of above 5 hectares. The average cultivated farmland was 2.68 hectares, which was the average amount of land that a farmer or farming households actively uses for farming. This clearly indicated that most of the members of farming household were smallholder farmers, which make them more vulnerable to climate shocks due to limited resources and scale. This corroborated by Ayinde *et al.* (2018) in a related study on vulnerability maize farmers to climate risk in Kwara State, Nigeria.

Table 4: Profiling of farm size cultivated by the farming household vulnerability (n = 703)

Household size	Wave 2		Wave 3		Wave 4		Pooled	
	Non-vulnerable	Vulnerable	Non-vulnerable	Vulnerable	Non-vulnerable	Vulnerable	Frequency	Percentage
<=1	44.60	48.32	39.20	50.99	47.74	46.22	329	46.80
1.01-3.0	19.51	12.98	16.80	15.01	14.29	16.48	110	15.65
3.01-5.0	20.91	19.47	23.60	18.10	22.56	18.54	141	20.06
Above 5	14.98	19.23	20.40	15.89	15.41	18.76	123	17.50
Mean							2.68	
Total	287	416	250	453	266	437	703	100.00

Source: Author’s Computation 2024

Table 5 revealed the labour utilization of the respondents of both non-vulnerable and vulnerable group in wave 2, wave 3 and wave 4. The results showed that most (83.97% of the non-vulnerable group and 84.62% of the non-vulnerable group) in wave 2, (86.80% of the non-vulnerable and 83.00% of the non-vulnerable group) in wave 3 and (84.21% of the non-vulnerable and 84.44% of the non-vulnerable group) in wave 4 made use of hired labor for their farm operations, approximately 7.3% and 8.9% of non-vulnerable and vulnerable respectively in wave 2, 7.6% and 8.6% of both side in wave 3 and 9.0% and 7.8% in wave 4 used family labour, while 8.71% of the non-vulnerable group and 6.49% of the vulnerable group in wave 2, 5.60% and 8.39% of both side respectively in wave 3 and 6.77% and 7.78% of both non-vulnerable and vulnerable group respectively in wave 4 opted for exchange labor. This implied that, across all waves and groups, hired labour was the primary method of labour utilization. Given the pattern of this result, one can infer that hired labor was mostly utilized by the farmers of farming households in the study area.

Table 5: Profiling of labour utilization by the farming household vulnerability (n = 703)

Labour utilization	Wave 2		Wave 3		Wave 4		Pooled	
	Non-vulnerable	Vulnerable	Non-vulnerable	Vulnerable	Non-vulnerable	Vulnerable	Frequency	Percentage
Exchange Labour	8.71	6.49	5.60	8.39	6.77	7.78	52	7.40
Family Labour	7.32	8.89	7.60	8.61	9.02	7.78	58	8.25
Hired Labour	83.97	84.62	86.80	83.00	84.21	84.44	593	84.35
Total	287	416	250	453	266	437	703	100.00

Source: Author's Computation 2024

Concerning the use of formal credit and informal credits, table 6 shows that larger proportion (92.03%) of the respondents did not have access to formal credit, while very few (7.97%) had access to formal credit across all the waves. Also, 58.04% of the respondents had access to informal credit, while 41.96% did not have. Among the non-vulnerable households in wave 2, 61.32% accessed informal credit, while 38.68% did not. For vulnerable households, 55.77% accessed informal credit, while 44.23% did not. Wave 3 non-vulnerable group revealed that 60.80% accessed informal credit while 39.20% did not. 56.51% of the vulnerable household accessed informal credit while 43.49% did not. Non-vulnerable household in wave 4 shows that, 60.15% accessed informal credit while 39.85% did not. 56.75% of vulnerable accessed informal credit while 43.25% did not. This implies that, informal credit appears to be a significant coping strategy for households, particularly in times of vulnerability to climate shocks or food insecurity.

Likewise, among wave 2 non-vulnerable households, 7.32% accessed formal credit, while 92.68% did not. 8.41% of vulnerable households accessed formal credit while 91.59% did not. 8.40% of wave 3 non-vulnerable group accessed formal credit while 91.60% did not. 7.73% vulnerable group accessed formal credit while 92.27% did not. In wave 4, 6.77% of non-vulnerable household accessed formal credit while 93.23% did not. 8.70% of vulnerable group accessed formal credit while 91.30% did not. This shows that, formal credit plays a very limited role in addressing the financial needs of both vulnerable and non-vulnerable farming households. This situation may limit farmers to expand their scale of production which could make household farmers more vulnerable to shocks and poverty condition. This result lends credence to the findings of Ubokudom *et al.* (2019) who also established that 95% of the farming households in South-South Nigeria lack access to formal credits.

Table 6: Profiling of access to credit of the farming household vulnerability (n = 703)

Access to credit	Wave 2		Wave 3		Wave 4		Pooled	
	Non-vulnerable	Vulnerable	Non-vulnerable	Vulnerable	Non-vulnerable	Vulnerable	Frequency	Percentage
Informal credit								
No	38.68	44.23	39.20	43.49	39.85	43.25	295	41.96
Yes	61.32	55.77	60.80	56.51	60.15	56.75	408	58.04
Total	287	416	250	453	266	437	703	100.00
Formal credit								
No	92.68	91.59	91.60	92.27	93.23	91.30	647	92.03
Yes	7.32	8.41	8.40	7.73	6.77	8.70	56	7.97
Total	287	416	250	453	266	437	703	100.00

Source: Author's Computation 2024

Households' status of vulnerability to climate shocks

The distribution of the farming household based on their status of vulnerability to climate shocks was shown in Table 7. Farmers were classified into their vulnerability status based on observed climate shocks across each of the waves under consideration. The results indicated that 416 respondents, representing (59.18%) of the farming households were vulnerable to climate shocks in wave 2, (453 respondents) which represents 64.44% were vulnerable to climate shocks in wave 3 while 62.16% (437 respondents) were vulnerable to climate shocks in wave 4. The average percentage across all waves was 61.93% which implies that, majority of the respondent in the study area were vulnerable to climate shocks. This result is in agreement with Oluwatayo and Ojo (2022) who in a related study also reported that 57.5% of farming households in South Africa were vulnerable to climate change.

Table 7: Profiling of household status of vulnerability to climate shocks

Vulnerability status	Wave 2		Wave3		Wave 4	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Vulnerable	416	59.18	453	64.44	437	62.16
Non-vulnerable	287	40.82	250	35.56	266	37.84
Total	703	100.00	703	100.00	703	100.00

Source: Author's Computation 2024

Vulnerability of the Farming Households to Food Insecurity

Vulnerability to food insecurity of the farming households was estimated using three-stage feasible generalized least squares (3-SFGLS). The linear regression was performed to see the effects of some of the explanatory variables of the ex-ante mean consumption. From the table, the model is statistically significant overall, but the low R-squared value indicates that it explains only about 5.66% of the variation in food consumption. This suggests that there are other important factors influencing food security not captured in this model. Table 14 shown the coefficients of marital status, formal education status, utilities and dependency ratio have the expected signs (that is, positive) and are statistically significant. The results also showed that wave 4 has a negative significant correlation with food consumption. This suggests that farming households were less vulnerable to food insecurity in wave 4 than wave 2 and wave 3 respectively, and as a result, the respondents experienced increased food demand for consumption in waves 2 and 3 than wave 4.

The co-efficients of married, utilities and dependency ratio were positively significant at 1%, 1% and 10% respectively which implied that as more married farming households, increase in utilities and dependency ratio, will induce increase in food consumption. Also, education of the household head has a positive correlation on food consumption and variance. This relationship is significant at 10% which shows that educated farming households are not more vulnerable to food insecurity in the future. This aligns with schultz's hypothesis that educated individuals are less vulnerable, and adapt more easily to changing circumstances. Likewise, poor rainfall is negatively significant at 10%, which implies that as rain fall reduces, vulnerability to food insecurity of the respondent increases.

In the 3FGLS regression, vulnerability to food insecurity were found to be higher with being a male gender, farm size, incidence of flooding, farmer-header's conflict and access to formal credit; these were all positively significant at 1% probability level. The results indicate that an increase in all these variables led to increase in vulnerability to food insecurity in wave 3 than wave 2. The positive and significant relationship of farm size with food insecurity was also established in a related study conducted by Agboola *et al.* (2004) who stated that the higher the

land size, the higher the expected food consumption will be. This observation may be as a result of the smallholding nature of farming operations by the respondents.

Age of the household head and distance nearest to market have significant and negative relationships with food insecurity. This means that older families were more vulnerable and as result of this, are more likely to face decreased food intake. Also, proximity to market, long distance of farming households to market are more likely leads to decreased food intake. This finding is in tandem with Ogunyemi, *et al.* (2022) who in their research on household coping strategies and the extent of vulnerability to food insecurity in Ekiti state, Nigeria, share similar opinion.

Table 8: Analysis using Three-stage Feasible Generalized Least Square

Variable	Linear Co-efficient	Regression Std.Err	T	3 FGLS Co-efficient	Std.Err	t
Age	-0.00204	0.0016	-1.31	-0.0441	5.6209	-7.81
Sex	0.00733	0.0512	0.14	0.1579	1.8007	8.81
Married	0.17355	0.6863	2.53	3.7778	2.3207	1.61
Distance to Market	-0.2331	0.0554	-0.42	-0.5044	1.6707	-3.01
Education	0.00887	0.0048	1.83	0.1919	1.7508	1.11
Utilities	0.00003	0.0000	3.22	0.0070	4.1211	1.71
Farm size	0.01253	0.0095	1.32	0.2710	3.3908	8.01
Flooding	0.13714	0.8914	1.54	2.9665	3.0907	9.61
Poor rain	-0.12731	0.0697	-1.83	-2.7414	2.3107	-1.21
Farmer herder' conflict	-0.09479	0.0771	-1.23	-2.0589	2.3607	8.71
Dependency ratio	0.01407	0.0075	1.88	0.3047	2.9708	1.01
Formal credits	0.12044	0.0895	1.35	2.5881	3.1507	8.31
Wave-2	-0.08378	0.1603	-0.52	-1.8357	5.8707	-3.11
Wave-3	0.20894	0.1489	1.40	4.5180	5.2507	8.61
Wave-4	-0.22057	0.0833	-2.65	-4.7360	3.3807	-1.41
-cons	11.14348	0.1448	75.98	124.1316	4.8407	2.61
Observation	703					
R²	=5.66%					

Source: Author's Computation 2024

Determinants of vulnerability to climate shocks

To examine the determinants of vulnerability to climate shocks, the measure of vulnerability was used to classify households as highly vulnerable and low vulnerable. Using the vulnerability indicator threshold, when vulnerability estimate is greater or equal to 0.5, the household is grouped as highly vulnerable, and takes a value of 1, and 0 otherwise (that is, when the vulnerability estimate is less than 0.5). The measurement of goodness of fit of the model also shows that the model fit the data well. On a general note, the model is significant at 1% level of significance and have a pseudo R^2 of 0.2098. The model explains about 21% of the variation in vulnerability to poverty, which is a moderate level of explanatory power for a logistic regression.

The factors that determined vulnerability to climate shocks is shown in table 9. These factors include years of formal education, food borrowing, farmer herder's conflict, dependency ratio and access to formal credit. The negative signs of marginal effects reduce probability of household vulnerability while the positive signs increase the level of vulnerability of the respondents. The food borrowing, farmer herder's conflict and dependency ratio were positively significant at 1%, 10%, 1%, respectively. This implies that increase in all these variables induces increase in vulnerability to climate shocks of the household farmers. Households' educational status and access to formal credit were both negative and statistically significant at 1% level. This implies that the probability of being vulnerable to climate shocks was low for the households that were more educated and had access to formal credit. An access to formal credit of an educated household reduces the probability of being highly vulnerable to climate shocks by 13 percent. This supports findings by Asravor (2018) on the importance of credit access for reducing farmer vulnerability in Ghana.

Results from the logistic regression also indicated that farming households in wave 2 and 3 had higher probability of vulnerability to climate shocks than wave 4. The coefficient of wave 4 is negative and highly significant statistically at 5% probability level. This shows that probability of being vulnerable to climate shocks in wave 4 was lower. This may be as a result of to the introduction and scaling-up of agricultural technologies introduced at one point or the other which provide farming households with buffer against climatic shocks and food insecurity. This finding

is corroborated by what Eyob Bekele (2012) also reported in a similar study conducted in Tigray Region, Ethiopia.

Table 9: Determinants of Vulnerability to Climate Shocks. The Discrete Change of Dummy Variable from 0 to 1

Variable	Logistic Coefficient	regression Std.Err	Z	Marginal effect dy/dx	Z
Age	0.002907	0.0062351	0.47	0.0005736	0.47
Sex	0.2487359	0.2031005	1.22	0.0487737	1.24
Dist near mark	0.159208	0.2278412	0.70	0.0314143	0.70
Education	-0.0638873	0.0194665	-3.28	-0.012606	-3.31
Farm size	0.052079	0.0365902	1.42	0.10276	1.42
Less food	0.0590757	0.1981304	0.30	0.011646	0.30
Borrow food	0.6967941	0.3252021	2.14	0.120422	2.53
Flooding	0.0302764	0.3523019	0.09	0.0060078	0.09
Poor rain	0.3238073	0.2585797	1.25	0.0609646	1.32
Farmer herder	0.5736468	0.2898638	1.98	0.1237723	1.85
Dependencyratio	0.4796539	0.0520628	9.21	0.0946435	10.98
Formal credit	-0.7922821	0.3439248	-2.30	-0.1314124	-2.82
Wave -2	-0.4281009	0.5961897	-0.72	0.0776355	-0.79
Wave -3	0.7772169	0.5977981	1.30	0.1714555	1.20
Wave -4	-0.8827358	0.37966	-2.33	-0.1473096	-2.81
_Cons	2.322166	0.5499344	4.28		

Number of obs	703
Log pseudo	-355.54852
Wald chi (15)	100.40
Prob > Chi	0.0000
Pseudo R ²	0.2098

Source: Author's Computation 2024

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, vulnerability to climate shocks among Nigerian farming households is driven by a combination of socio-economic and environmental factors. Households with better education and access to formal credit are less vulnerable, while those facing poor rainfall, flooding, and farmer-herder conflicts are more likely to experience food insecurity.

It was recommended that farming household heads should engage in more formal education in order to reduce their vulnerability. Farmers should practice irrigation and dry season farming in order to reduce food insecurity. Farmers and Herders should settle their conflicts amicably in order to reduce food insecurity. The findings recommend the critical need for targeted interventions to enhance the adaptive capacity of smallholder farmers.

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